

MODELING AND ANALYSIS OF OPTIMIZED RECTANGULAR RC COLUMNS CONFINED WITH CFRP COMPOSITES

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Abstract - The structural behavior of rectangular reinforced concrete (RC) columns confined with different configurations of carbon fiber reinforcement polymers (CFRP) sheets is investigated by using nonlinear finite element analysis (NLFEA). SOLID65, LINK8, SOLID45, and SOLID46 elements represented the concrete, steel bars, steel plates, and CFRP sheets, respectively. Based on each simulated component's actual characteristics, the nonlinear material properties are defined for each type of elements. The NLFEA results clearly confirmed that the use of CFRP composites strengthening system for RC columns improves the ductility and ultimate axial strength capacity. The enhancement in the ductility and axial strength increased with the increasing of the number of CFRP composite layers. The CFRP composite strengthening system of rectangular RC columns can be categorized as efficient and successful only if significant increase in the ultimate axial strength capacity is achieved. As confirmed by the results of this study, NLFEA can efficiently simulate the structural behavior of rectangular RC columns confined with CFRP sheets. It is recommended that the NLFEA model can be used in additional research studies to develop design guidelines and rules for RC structural elements strengthened with CFRP composites.

Keywords - NLFEA, CFRP, Simulation, RC Columns.

I. INTRODUCTION

Strengthening, repairing and seismic retrofitting of reinforced concrete (RC) structures with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites has become enormously promising composite materials due to its light weight, high strength, and ease of application. There are many engineering strengthening applications in which CFRP was externally bonded onto the surface of RC elements to improve their ductility and strength [1-4]. In order to better understand the mechanical mechanism, the behavior of confined RC columns with CFRP sheets needs further investigated. Modeling of the complex nonlinear behavior of RC rectangular column is a challenge in the FEA of structural concrete elements. Therefore, few researchers attempted to simulate the behavior of RC externally strengthened with FRP composites using FEA [5-15]. In this study, the ANSYS finite element program [16] was used to simulate the behavior and the effectiveness of various configurations of CFRP confinement of the rectangular RC columns. Actual geometry and steel reinforcing details of experimentally tested rectangular column specimens as well as the used strengthening configuration and the number of the externally bonded CFRP layers were considered in the NLFEA. The load-deflection response, load-strain response, and failure mode were obtained for each specimen by the NLFEA and compared to the companion experimental test results.

II. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Element SOLID65 was used to model the concrete

material without steel reinforcing bars. The element is capable to crack in three orthogonal directions, crush, creep, and plastically deforms [16]. The ultimate uniaxial tensile strength of 4.5 MPa, compressive strength of 55 MPa, and initial young's modulus (E_c) = 35063 MPa are needed to define a failure surface for the concrete. As a result, William and Warnke (1975) [17] was used to defined the concrete criterion for failure of the concrete due to a multiaxial stress state as shown in Figure 1(a). Also, Poisson's ratio of 0.2 shear transfer coefficient (β_t) of 0.2 [18] were used in this study.

A 3-D spar element (LINK8) was used to model the steel bars with a uniaxial tension-compression behavior and is also capable of plastic deformation [16]. An elastic-perfectly plastic material is assumed for steel which is identical in tension and compression as shown in Fig. 1(b). The Poisson's ratio and steel yield stress are 0.3 and 413 MPa. A SOLID45 (eight-node solid element) was used for the supports and load application steel plates [16] to provide an even stress distribution over the support and loading areas. A linear elastic material with an elastic modulus equal to 200 GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3 were assumed for steel plates. Finally, layered element (SOLID46) was used to model the CFRP composite sheet which has orthotropic material properties in each layer [16] with a thickness of 0.165 mm, elastic modulus of 228 GPa, tensile strength of 4275 MPa, and ultimate tensile strain of 0.017 mm/mm in the fibers direction. Firstly, the quarter of the column was simulated to study the behavior by taking benefit of symmetry of the column geometry and loading with proper boundary conditions which reduces the computer disk space requirements and computing time. At both column ends, one end was

modeled as pin support while the translation and rotation in the loading direction were only allowed at the other column end. In order to determine the appropriate mesh density (Fig. 2), a convergence study was carried out.

(a) Concrete

(b) Steel reinforcement
Fig. 1 Stress-Strain curve

Perfect bonding between the concrete and steel reinforcement as well as between CFRP composite and concrete was assumed. Rectangular RC columns with a length of 750 mm and cross section of 125 mm×150 mm, were simulated in order to model the response of confined rectangular RC columns with various configurations of CFRP sheets under axial loading. All the columns were reinforced longitudinally with 4#10 steel bars and laterally with steel ties of 5 mm diameter at a spacing of 125 mm except at the ends (25 mm spacing), and this is due to the stress concentration at the ends. Also, these critical ends were additionally strengthened with two layers of CFRP composite sheets for a distance of 125 mm. The cross-section, reinforcement details, and the CFRP composite confinement configurations of the columns are shown in Fig. 3. The applied vertical load was divided up to failure into a series of small load increments of 0.45 kN. Convergence at the end of each load increment was checked by using Newton-Raphson equilibrium iterations. Failure of each column model was identified when the solution for a vertical load increment of 0.0045 kN was not converging.

(a) Quarter of the column

(b) Steel reinforcement

Fig. 2 Typical finite element meshing quarter of the column

Fig. 3 Cross section and reinforcement details

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Load-Displacement Response

The characteristics of the CFRP confined columns were evaluated based on the load-displacement behavior. Fig. 4 shows the NLFEA axial load versus axial displacement curves of the simulated columns. The ultimate loads were 1072, 1588, 1659, 1757, 1817, 1912, 1968, and 2046 kN as shown in Table 1. The corresponding increase in the ultimate axial load with respect to the control specimens was 48%, 55%, 64%, 70%, 78%, 84%, and 90%, respectively. The axial load–displacement curves shown in Fig. 4 reveal that there is a significant increase in the ultimate axial load as well as in the ultimate axial displacement when confining the columns with CFRP sheets. Fig. 4 also shows that the increase in the ultimate loads and displacements is directly related to an increase in the number of CFRP sheet layers.

TABLE I: ANSYS results at ultimate

Confinement Configuration	Ultimate load, kN	Percentage of increase in ultimate load with respect to control specimen (%)
Control (unconfined)	1072	---
1-layer in the transverse direction (1T)	1588	48.1
1-layer in the transverse direction and 1-layer in the longitudinal (1TIL(OUT))	1659	54.8
2-layers in the transverse direction (2T)	1757	63.9
1-layer in the longitudinal and 1-layer in the transverse direction (1TIL(in))	1817	69.5
3-layers in the transverse direction (3T)	1912	78.4
1-layer in the longitudinal and 2-layers in the transverse direction (2TIL(in))	1968	83.6
4-layers in the transverse direction (4T)	2046	90.6

B. Load-Strain Response

The axial and circumferential strains at the critical region of the columns were plotted versus the axial load as shown in Fig. 5. The axial load-axial strain response followed a similar trend as the axial load-axial displacement for each specimen type. At failure, the circumferential strain readings of the confined columns were greater than 0.017 mm/mm, which is the maximum strain capacity of the carbon fiber. The circumferential strain results are coinciding with the observed failure mode of the confined columns, the failures did not occur before the fracturing of the CFRP sheets.

This reveals that the effectiveness of the CFRP confinement was good. Based on the NLFEA results shown in Figs. 4 and 5, it can be observed that confinement of rectangular RC column with CFRP significantly enhances its strength and ductility performance under axial loading. Typical distribution of CFRP sheet and concrete strains at control and confinement columns were shown in Figs. 6-13.

Fig. 4 Axial loads versus axial displacements

Fig. 5 Axial load versus axial and circumferential strain curves

Fig. 6 Strain and stress contours of control column

Fig. 7 Strain contours with one layer in the transverse direction

Fig. 8 Strain contours with 2 layers in the transverse direction

Fig. 9 Strain contours with 3 layers in the transverse direction

Fig. 10 Strain contours with 4 layers in the transverse direction

Fig. 11 Strain contours of column with one layer in the longitudinal (out) and one in the transverse direction

Fig. 12 Strain contours of column with one layer in the longitudinal (in) and one in the transverse direction

Fig. 13 Strain contours of column with one in the longitudinal (in) with two in the transverse direction

CONCLUSION

Externally bonded CFRP sheets are very effective in enhancing the axial strength and deformation capacity of concrete columns. Increasing the number of CFRP sheet layers leads to a significant increase in the ultimate axial strength and a slight increase in the ultimate displacement. Also, two CFRP sheet layers is the optimum number of CFRP layers and this is based on the load strain behavior. Higher axial loads and strains at failure were recorded for the confined RC columns wrapped with CFRP in comparison with the unconfined ones. This finite element model can be used in additional studies to develop design rules for strengthening RC columns using CFRP composites.

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